

Potentiometric Study of Transition Metal Complexes of Nitro-Salicylic Acids

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The interactions between Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II) and Zn(II) with 3-nitro, 5-nitro and 3 : 5-dinitrosalicylic acids have been studied in aqueous medium at 0.1 M ionic strength and at 30° by following the Calvin-Bjerrum potentiometric titration technique. It is observed that Cu(II) forms 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with all the three ligands while the remaining metal ions form only 1 : 1 complexes. The formation constants of the transitional metal complexes follow Irving-Williams order and show dependence on the basicities of the ligands.

Salicylic and 5-sulfosalicylic acid complexes of transitional metal ions are investigated to a great extent¹. However, a systematic study of various substituted salicylic acid complexes with these metal ions is still lacking. Recently Khadikar and Ameria² reported the study of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes of 3-nitrosalicylic acid in 25–75% v/v water-dioxane solvent medium. We have undertaken investigation of transition metal complexes of a number of substituted salicylic acids. This paper forms a part of this work and deals with the transition metal complexes of two mononitro and one dinitro salicylic acids.

Materials : All chemicals such as sodium hydroxide, sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid were of analytical reagent grade. The ligands 3-nitro, 5-nitro and 3 : 5-dinitrosalicylic acids were obtained from B.D.H. (India). The metal ions were used in the form of their perchlorates which were prepared by dissolving the metal carbonates in perchloric acid. The concentration of metal ions in a solution was determined by EDTA titration³.

Potentiometric measurements : Beckman model H-2 pH meter was used for the measurement of pH. The accuracy of pH meter is ± 0.02 pH. It was calibrated by buffer solutions at pH 4.01 and 9.11 (30°).

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure involved Calvin-Bjerrum potentiometric titrations of carbonate-free solutions of (i) free HClO₄ ($2.0 \times 10^{-2}M$), (ii) free HClO₄+ligand ($2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$), (iii) free HClO₄+ligand ($2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$)+metal perchlorate ($4.0 \times 10^{-4}M$), and (iv) free HClO₄ ($2.0 \times 10^{-2}M$)+metal perchlorate ($4.0 \times 10^{-4}M$). The ionic strength of each solution was maintained constant at 0.1M ionic strength by the addition of an appropriate amount of 1M NaClO₄ solution. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen-free nitrogen gas through the titration assembly containing the electrodes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The possibility of complex formation was initially examined by noting (i) the pH of hydrolysis of a metal ion which can be known from the point of departure of the metal curve from that of the acid curve and (ii) the pH at which the metal complex titration curve deviated from the ligand curve. The data presented in Table 1. reveal that for all the metal ions the complexation started at lower pH than the pH of hydrolysis. The possibility of formation of polynuclear species was neglected since the solutions employed were very dilute.

TABLE 1

Metal ion	pH at the commencement of hydrolysis	pH at the commencement of complex formation
Cu(II)	5.5	3.5
Ni(II)	6.2	4.0
Co(II)	6.5	4.5
Mn(II)	7.0	5.8
Zn(II)	6.9	5.5

Irving and Rossotti's expression⁴ was used for the calculations of \bar{n}_A values which were used to determine the pK values of $-COOH$ (pK_1) and $-OH$ (pK_2) groups. The pK values were calculated by pointwise calculations. Our values given in Table 2 are in good agreement with the literature values^{5,6}. Metal-ligand formation number \bar{n}_A was calculated

TABLE 2

pK values of the ligands

Ligand	pK_1		pK_2	
	Observed	Reported	Observed	Reported
3-nitro salicylic acid	1.80	1.82 ⁶	10.22	10.33 ⁵
5-nitro salicylic acid	2.20	2.12 ⁵	10.13	10.34 ⁵
3 : 5-dinitrosalicylic acid	1.31	—	7.00	—

from the Irving and Rossotti expression⁴. The maximum value of \bar{n} obtained before the pH of precipitation as observed in metal complex titrations were 1.85, 1.05, 0.81, 0.74 and 0.99 for Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II) and Zn(II) complexes. It was, therefore, concluded that except Cu(II) the remaining metal ions form only 1 : 1 complexes. pL values, where $[L]$ is free ligand concentration, were calculated and stability constants were determined by pointwise calculations. These values are presented in Table 3.

Pauling⁷ has suggested that the pK values of phenolic $-OH$ in nitrophenol should be less compared to that of phenol by a factor of $\log 45$ for every nitro group substituted in the meta position and by a factor of $\log 1000$ for every nitro group in the ortho and the para

TABLE 3

Metal-ligand stability constants (log K₁)

Metal-ion	3-nitro S.A.	5-nitro S.A.	3 : 5-dinitro S.A.
Mn(II)	4.85	4.41	3.06
Co(II)	5.24	5.18	3.63
Ni(II)	5.96	5.36	4.11
Cu(II)	8.12	7.99	6.70
Zn(II)	5.73	5.38	3.32
log K ₂ for Cu(II)	5.87	5.38	4.95

positions due to resonance interaction. The pK₂ for salicylic acid being 13.30⁸, it can be observed that pK₂ values for nitro substitution at 3 and 5 positions and that at 3 : 5 positions agree well with Pauling's suggestions. Further it was observed that the nitro group affects the -OH dissociation to a larger extent than -COOH dissociation. This is due to the fact that (i) for a nitro group the inductive effect will fall off with the distance as we go from *o-m-p* and (ii) nitro group will show electron withdrawing mesomeric effect from ortho and para but not from meta position.

The stability constants of metal complexes of each ligand show the order :— Mn(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II). This confirms the validity of Irving-Williams order for these complexes. The chelating tendency of the ligands for a particular metal ion follows the order : 3-nitro > 5-nitro > 3 : 5-dinitro salicylic acids. This is in accordance with the basicity of -OH group from which H⁺ ions are displaced during complexation.

The ratio of log K₁/K₂ for Cu(II) complexes of 3 : 5-dinitro, 3-nitro, 5-nitro salicylic acids are 1.75, 2.25 and 2.61 respectively. The lower value for 3-nitro and 3 : 5-dinitro complexes than that of 5-nitro may be due to the steric hindrance offered during complexation by bulky nitro group ortho to the -OH group.

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